

A novel ionophoretic technique in the study of binary and ternary metal-4-hydroxybenzoate complexes

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Ionophoretic technique has been used for the study of Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}-4-hydroxybenzoate binary and Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}-4-hydroxybenzoate NTA (nitrilotriacetic acid) ternary complexes. The stability constants of metal-4-hydroxybenzoate binary complexes are found to be 10^{3.57}, 10^{2.46}, 10^{2.43} and 10^{2.40} and the stability constants of metal-4-hydroxybenzoate-NTA ternary complexes have been found to be 10^{5.70}, 10^{5.65}, 10^{5.55} and 10^{5.50} for Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes respectively at $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄) and 25°C.

Migration of ions of pure electrolyte solution has been widely studied but the migration in mixed electrolyte solutions has not as yet been much investigated. This paper deals with latter aspect.

In the present communication an effort has been made to assess the stability constants of mononuclear binary and ternary complexes formed in a system containing various electrolyte ingredients. A simple ionophoretic tube¹ has been designed which after standardization yield remarkable results.

Results and discussion

Metal-4-hydroxybenzoic acid binary systems :

Fig. 1 illustrates the relationship between absorbance difference and the pH's and thus gives an idea of the change of overall mobility of the metal ion species with change in hydrogen ion status of the system containing Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, and Co^{II}-4-hydroxybenzoic acid. The first plateau in each case corresponds to a region of pH where metal ions are uncomplexed. Further increase of pH from this region onward which naturally leads to increase in ligating 4-hydroxybenzoic acid anion concentration [HL⁻] and brings about a progressive decrease in over all ionic mobility of the metal ion species. This decrease indicates formation of complex of the metal ion with the ligand. A point is reached beyond which mobility of the metal ion species remain constant regardless of the increase of pH of reaction mixture. This is the second plateau which corresponds to a pH region in which 1 : 1 complex is predominantly formed. Beyond this plateau increase of pH has no effect and mobility remain constant.

The overall mobility U is a composite parameter contributed by different ionic species of the metal ion and is given by following equation :

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1 K_1 [L] + u_2 K_1 K_2 [L]^2 + \dots}{1 + K_1 [L] + K_1 K_2 [L]^2 + \dots}$$

where K 's are the stability constant of complexes and $[L]$ is the concentration of 4-hydroxybenzoic acid anion. u 's (u_0 , u_1 , u_2) are the ionic mobilities of different species of the metal ions which can be assessed from the plateau's of the figure. In the region between first and second plateau the system contain overwhelmingly a mixture of free metal ion and 1 : 1 complex. The existence of 1 : 2 complex can be excluded and hence the third term in the numerator and the denominator of the above equation can be justifiably neglected. U would be equal to $(u_0 + u_1)/2$ provided $K_1[L] = 1$. Accordingly the pH corresponding to the average value of u_0 and u_1 is found from the figure and with the knowledge of the dissociation constants of 4-hydroxybenzoic acid ($pK_1 = 4.58$ and $pK_2 = 9.46$)² the concentration of 4-hydroxybenzoic acid ion at this pH is calculated. It's reciprocal gives the stability constant K of the 1 : 1 complex which are reported in Table 1.

Metal-4-hydroxybenzoic acid-NTA ternary systems :

Fig. 2 depicts the observation of studies carried out in 4-hydroxybenzoic acid-NTA ternary complexes. These graphs clearly show the formation of two plateaus in each cases. The first plateau corresponds to binary 4-hydroxybenzoic acid complexes whereas the second plateau corresponds to the formation of new complex.

Fig. 1. Mobility curve, metal-4-hydroxybenzoic acid systems : (♦) Fe, (■) Cu, (Δ) Ni, (●) Co.

Fig. 2. Mobility curve, metal-4-hydroxybenzoic acid-NTA systems : (♦) Fe, (■) Cu, (Δ) Ni, (●) Co.

This new complex may be mixed complexes of the type M-L-NTA or pure M-NTA complex. But with the help of related graphs of M-NTA complexes it was found that the absorbance difference in case of new complex is not identical to M-NTA pure complex. Further this ternary complex has greater mobility than that of binary 4-hydroxybenzoic

complex hence these observations confirms the formation of mixed M-L-NTA complex.

For M-L-NTA complexes the stability constant K' is calculated by using modified equation.

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1 K [NTA]}{1 + K [NTA]}$$

Singh *et al.* : A novel ionophoretic technique in the study of binary and ternary metal-4-hydroxybenzoate complexes here u_0 and u_1 are the mobilities of ML and M-L-NTA complexes.

From the figures concentration of NTA at which overall mobility is the mean of the mobilities of the two plateaus is determined. The concentration of NTA anion at pH 7.0 for this NTA concentration is calculated. K' is obviously equal to $1/[NTA]$. All these values are also reported in Table 1 and clearly indicates the superior coordinating power of NTA anion to other dicarboxylic acid species.

Table 1. Stability constants of metal-4-hydroxybenzoic acid and M-4-hydroxybenzoic acid-NTA complexes

Metal ion	Stability constant values	
	M-L	M-L-NTA
Fe ^{III}	3.57	5.70
Cu ^{II}	2.46	5.65
Ni ^{II}	2.43	5.55
Co ^{II}	2.40	5.50

The stability constant values of Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} are in the order : Fe^{III} > Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II}, which follows the Irving-William's³ order for the stability constant of transition metal of first transition series.

Experimental

Metal-4-hydroxybenzoic acid binary systems :

One set of 15 ml solution each containing 1×10^{-3} M Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, 0.1 M HClO₄ and 1×10^{-2} M 4-hydroxybenzoic acid was prepared at different pH's value (by adding NaOH solution). In case of Fe^{III}, 1×10^{-4} M Fe^{III}, 0.1 M HClO₄ and 1×10^{-3} M 4-hydroxybenzoic acid was used 10 ml of this solution is taken in an electrophoretic tube and then thermostated at 25°C. The tube (18 cm long and 5 mm bore) with a stopper in the middle was fused perpendicularly at the ends with short wider tubes of 1.2 cm bore. The position of the tube was adjusted in such a way that the level of the solution in one wide end arm reached a circular mark on it. This adjustment fixed the volume of the solution on both sides of the middle stopper. Two (0.5 × 0.5 cm) platinum electrodes were dipped in each arm cup and a 50 V potential difference was applied between them. Electrolysis of the solution was allowed for 45 min, after which the middle stopper of the tube is closed. The solution of the anodic compartment was taken out in a 15 ml flask. The copper content of the solution was converted into copper thiocyanate⁴. The volume was raised to a mark in the flask and the absorbance at 408 nm was measured with CZ-

specol spectrophotometer. The Co^{II} content of the anodic compartment was converted into cobalt-thiocyanate⁴ complex and absorbance at 625 nm was measured after making up the volume to 15 ml. The Ni^{II} content was converted to nickel dimethyl glyoximate⁵ and absorbance was taken at 445 nm. Similarly the Fe^{III} content of the anodic compartment was converted to Fe thiocyanate⁵ complex and absorbance was measured at 480 nm against a reagent blank. These observations are graphically represented in Fig. 1.

Metal-NTA binary systems :

The experiments for binary complexes of Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}-NTA are prerequisite for the study of metal-4-hydroxybenzoic acid-NTA ternary complexes. These studies have been carried out by Sameena⁶ and Patel⁷. The observations and results of these studies have been taken from there for comparison of observations found for ternary complexes.

Metal-4-hydroxybenzoic acid-NTA ternary systems :

The study of ternary complexes was carried out by progressive addition of secondary ligand NTA from 1×10^{-6} M to 1×10^{-2} M at a fixed pH 7.0 to a mixture of metal ion and 1×10^{-2} M 4-hydroxybenzoic acid and 0.1 M perchloric acid. The reason behind keeping the reaction mixture at pH 7.0 is that much ahead of this pH the simple binary complexes of metal 4-hydroxybenzoic acid and M-NTA are formed and remain intact even beyond this pH. The amount of secondary ligand NTA was increased each time in the electrophoretic tube and the electrolysis of the solution and it's observations were recorded each time as it was done in case of binary complexes. These observations are graphically represented in Fig. 2.

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